

PLASTIC YIELDING CONTRIBUTION TO FRACTURE TOUGHNESS OF POLYMERS MODIFIED WITH RUBBER AND INORGANIC FILLERS

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ABSTRACT

High multiaxial stress fields are created in front of a crack which lead to various fracture processes in a region close to the crack tip. One of these is matrix yielding around particles which may happen before debonding of the particles and that is the subject of this contribution. A hybrid composite consisting of a brittle polymer matrix and two filler components which are very different in size are considered. The larger particles are enclosed in a material consisting of matrix and nano-size rubber particles which form an effective material. At first the mechanical problem of a local composite element consisting of a stiff spherical particle within a spherical elastic-plastic rubber filled matrix under uniform tensile stress was solved. This implies the approximation of the triaxial stress state by a hydrostatic one. Because the stiff larger particles are not allowed to debond from the matrix it was assumed that the volume increase during loading of the local composite element is caused by elastic volume change and plastic dilatation of the voided effective matrix material. With the knowledge of the stresses and displacements of such a local composite element, the yielding energy around one particle was calculated. Finally an analytical equation for the composite fracture toughness for this mechanism was obtained by integration over the stress field of the crack within the dissipation zone. Fracture toughness increases with increasing volume fraction of inorganic micro-size particles towards a maximum.

1 INTRODUCTION

Filled polymer composites have been studied extensively because of their technological and scientific importance. A survey of major results in this field for inorganic fillers was given in the reviews by Moloney et al. [1] and Fu et al. [2]. The incorporation of rubber particles into brittle type polymers as, for example, polycarbonate and thermosets as epoxy, leads to an improved toughness. An effective way to improve toughness and at the same time stiffness and strength is to incorporate additional inorganic fillers to the rubber particle filled brittle type polymers. These effects were summarized and reviewed by Garg and Mai [3]. Huang and Kinloch [4] found that debonding of the rubber particles from the epoxy matrix or voiding of the rubber particles with subsequent void yielding of the matrix enhance fracture toughness. Inconsistent results about dissipation mechanisms and their influence on fracture toughness reveal that there is still need for more research. Recently Tang et al. [5] examined ternary epoxy composites filled with silica nanoparticles (average diameter of 20 nm) and rubber particles with diameters of 200-700 nm. All ternary composites showed much higher fracture toughness than the composites with only one filler component. It was concluded that the localized plastic deformation around the crack tip might be responsible for this improvement. However, Liu et al. [6] reported that “no synergistic effects on toughness are found in the hybrid nanocomposite studied”.

The present paper models a hybrid composite, consisting of microsize particles and nanosize rubber particles (or inorganic nanoparticle) filled neat polymer matrix. During loading of a fracture mechanical specimen, the nanoparticles are assumed to debond from the matrix or in case of rubber nanoparticles start voiding while the microparticles remain bonded to the matrix. After rubber voiding the regions between these particles start local yielding with necking. Herein this stress field is reduced

to a hydrostatic one. Next step is the calculation of the specific yielding energy density of all particles within the dissipation zone as a function of the applied hydrostatic stress. The contribution of plastic yielding to the fracture toughness of the composite is obtained by the integration over this stress, because it is highest near the crack tip and decreases towards the dissipation zone edge. Summing up this dissipation energy with the crack resistance of the effective matrix (filled neat matrix with rubber particles) met by the propagating crack, provides eventually the composite fracture toughness.

2 COMPOSITE MODEL

A hybrid composite consisting of a brittle polymer matrix such as thermoset or polycarbonate matrix, and two filler components which are very different in diameter (difference of about a factor of 100 in mean diameter) was considered. The smaller filler is rubber or may be an inorganic material as, for example, silica or glass particles. The larger particles are enclosed in a material consisting of neat matrix and the nanoparticles which form an effective material, cf. Fig. 1.

Figure 1: Composite consisting of glassy polymer matrix with small rubber particles (nanoparticles) and large (microsize) inorganic particles (microparticles). Adapted from Ref. [9].

For epoxy moulding compounds with micro-silica and fumed silica nanoparticles Han and Cho [7] could experimentally show, that the micro-silica particles are covered by deformed matrix. This means that the particles are bonded to the matrix and the crack moves within the matrix material, which is assumed also in our investigation.

The Young's modulus of neat matrix material is designed by $E_{m,0}$ and that one of the nanoparticles (rubber) by E_r . The typical radius of nanorubber fillers lies at about $r_r \approx 50-100nm$, cf. [7], and the volume fraction within the effective matrix (neat matrix with nanofillers) is given by v_r .

The mechanical properties of this effective material can be calculated by different approaches. With the Halpin-Tsai equation for spherical inclusions, the effective Young's modulus, E_m , of a material consisting of neat matrix, with the Young's modulus, $E_{m,0}$, and a spherical reinforcement, with the Young's modulus, E_r , is given by: $E_m = E_{m,0}(1 + 2\eta v_r)/(1 - \eta v_r)$ with $\eta = (E_r/E_{m,0} - 1)/(E_r/E_{m,0} + 2)$. The effective Poisson's ratio is assumed to remain unchanged: $\nu_m \approx \nu_{m,0}$. The effective matrix material is assumed to behave elastic-ideal plastic as the neat matrix.

This effective matrix material is filled with a second kind of particles, of modulus E_p and Poisson's ratio, ν_p , much larger than the rubber with a particle radius of about $r_p \approx 25\mu m$ and the volume fraction, v , in the composite. This composite has a Young's modulus of E_c and it can be calculated again with the properties of the components by the Halpin-Tsai equation: $E_c = E_m(1 + 2\eta v)/(1 - \eta v)$ with $\eta = (E_p/E_m - 1)/(E_p/E_m + 2)$.

Now the local situation around one of the spherical microparticle within a spherical volume of the effective matrix material of radius, r_0 , is considered in detail. This composite element, placed at the

position: ρ, φ, z in front of the crack, is shown in Fig. 2 and posses a local particle volume fraction of $\tilde{v} = (r_p / r_0)^3$. The radius, r_0 , describes the limit extension to ensure that the stress field of one large particle does not interact with other large particles.

Figure 2: Geometrical model (called composite element) of a spherical microparticle (placed at the position: ρ, φ in front of the crack) within effective matrix. Adapted from Ref. [9].

The model is sensitive to this parameter \tilde{v} and stress field calculations of particle-particle interaction as well as statistical considerations are necessary to find the relation to the particle volume fraction in the composite, v .

The interference of the stress fields of the larger particles with that one of the much smaller ones was neglected. At the outer surface, $r=r_0$, this volume element was loaded with the hydrostatic stress, σ_0 . The mechanical problem was described with spherical coordinates, r, θ, φ , most appropriate for this geometry, whereby the hydrostatic stresses in Cartesian coordinates were replaced by that one in spherical coordinates.

It is assumed that the debonding strength, σ_d , at the interface between the larger inorganic particles and the neat matrix material is larger than the matrix yield strength, σ_{my} .

For small loads, the effective matrix material behaves elastically, and with increasing stress it starts to yield. While loading such a composite element yielding begins at the radius where the yield condition is first satisfied, which assumes in the simplest case that the maximum shear stress reaches a critical value. The Tresca yield condition was used:

$$\sigma_r^{my} - \sigma_\theta^{my} = \sigma_{my} \quad \text{with } \sigma_r^{my} > \sigma_\theta^{my} \quad \text{and} \quad \sigma_\theta^{my} = \sigma_\phi^{my} \quad (1)$$

where the index “my” of the radial, hoop and circumferential stresses (more details in chapter 4) indicates the effective matrix yielding region and σ_{my} is the yield strength of the effective matrix material.

Under the given hydrostatic stress at the composite element, yielding is only possible if the effective matrix material shows plastic dilatation and this is only possible if the rubber particles cavitate or the nanofillers debond from the matrix. Thus it is assumed that the volume increase during loading of the composite element is caused by elastic volume change and plastic dilatation of the voided effective matrix material. This process is sketched in Fig. 3 for the region close to a large particle.

Figure 3: Volume segment near the large inorganic particle under the action of stress, cavitated rubber particles cause plastic dilatation of the effective matrix. Adapted from Ref. [9].

If there would be no cavitation of nanoparticles around the bonded microparticles, the volume would increase during plastic yielding of the material, but during plastic yielding the matrix volume has to remain constant. If the true triaxial stress state in front of the crack would be used instead of the hydrostatic one, then this supposition of cavitation or voiding of the nanoparticles can be dropped but the calculations would become much more elaborate without changing the qualitative results.

The stress field and the displacements of the composite element are calculated in chapter 4. The energy around a single particle and the total dissipation energy will be the content of chapter 5.

3 COMPOSITE FRACTURE TOUGHNESS

The energy necessary to initiate crack propagation is called crack resistance, R_c , or fracture toughness. During crack growth, the crack consumes energy, R_{pz} , to form the new fracture surface in the process zone. At the same time energy, R_{dz} , is dissipated by matrix yielding around debonded particles within a larger zone of width, $2\rho_y$, subsequently called the yielding zone, see Fig. 4.

Figure 4: Volume segment near the large inorganic particle under the action of stress, cavitated rubber particles cause plastic dilatation of the effective matrix. Adapted from Ref. [9].

The crack spreads over a small area dA of unit thickness. Summation of the process zone energy, given by the product of matrix toughness, R_m , and the relevant volume fraction, v_m , and the dissipation zone energy, as the integral over all local contributions, provides composite fracture toughness:

$$R_c = R_{pz} + R_{dz} = R_m v_m + 2 \int_0^{\rho_y} \eta_{my}(\rho) d\rho \quad (2)$$

where η_{my} is the volume specific matrix yielding energy, ρ is the distance coordinate from the crack tip. Under remote mode I loading of a specimen a multiaxial stress field is developed in front of a crack, which can be written as a function of the coordinates (ρ, φ) as: $\sigma_{c,ij} = (R_c E_c / \rho)^{1/2} g_{ij}(\varphi)$, (i,j=x,y,z) with E_c as the Young's modulus of the composite. To simplify the following derivations it was assumed that this multiaxial stress state at the position ρ can be approximated by a uniform radial tensile stress, σ_0 :

$$\sigma_0(\rho) = (\beta R_c E_c / \rho)^{1/2} \quad (3)$$

where β , as a zone shape and size factor, can be used as a fitting parameter. A similar approach was used by Zappalorto et al. [8], who argued that the hydrostatic stress component of the crack tip stress field is of major importance for such analysis. The parameter was β used to consider this quantitative deficiency in the true values of stresses. Consequently the half width of the dissipation zone, ρ_y , is given by:

$$\rho_y = \beta R_c E_c / \sigma_{0,\min}^2 \quad (4)$$

with $\sigma_{0,\min}$ as the minimum radial stress where plastic yielding in the matrix shell around a particle starts. The integration over the distance, ρ , from the crack plane can be transformed into integration over the stress. With the substitution: $d\rho = -2\beta R_c E_c (\sigma_0)^{-3} d\sigma_0$ and the normalization, $s = \sigma_0 / \sigma_{my}$, the integral in Eq. (2) can be rewritten as:

$$R_{dz} = 4\beta R_c E_c \frac{1}{\sigma_{my}^2} \int_{s_1}^{s_2} \eta_{my}(s) (s)^{-3} ds \quad (5)$$

with s_1 and s_2 as defined below. It was considered that very close to the crack tip, i.e. for $\rho \rightarrow 0$, where the stresses approach mathematically infinity according to: $\sigma_0(\rho) = (\beta R_c E_c / \rho)^{1/2}$, in reality the stress remains limited to the value $s_2 = s_{\max}$ for maximum yielding area around one particle.

4 THE MECHANICAL PROBLEM

4.1 Elastic solution

The stress equilibrium at the composite element is given by the differential equation:

$$\frac{\partial \sigma_r^k}{\partial r} = \frac{2}{r} (\sigma_\theta^k - \sigma_r^k) \quad \text{and} \quad \sigma_\theta^k = \sigma_\phi^k \quad (6)$$

with $\sigma_r^k, \sigma_\theta^k, \sigma_\phi^k$ as normal, hoop and the circumferential stress, respectively, where the index k=p, m indicates the particle and the elastic effective matrix. Their solution is known as the Lamè solution. With the boundary conditions of stresses and displacements the displacement at the outer region $u_0 = u^{me}(r = r_0)$, was obtained:

$$u_0 = \frac{r_0}{E_m} \sigma_0 C_0(E_p / E_m, \tilde{\nu}, \nu_p, \nu_m) \quad (7)$$

with C_0 as a function of structural and mechanical properties; for more details cf. Ref. [9].

4.1 Matrix yielding

When the hydrostatic stress, σ_0 , reaches a critical value, matrix yielding starts at the particle/matrix interface as soon as the yield condition is satisfied. The stresses within the region of matrix yielding obey the yield law given in Eq. (1), and the stress equilibrium, Eq. (6), in this case takes the form:

$$\frac{\partial \sigma_r^{my}}{\partial r} = -\frac{2}{r} \sigma_{my} \quad (8)$$

with the solution:

$$\sigma_r^{my} = A_{my} - \sigma_{my} \ln(r/r_p)^2 \quad (9)$$

with A_{my} as an integration constant. To calculate the stress distribution over the whole matrix ($r_p \leq r \leq r_0$) with elastic and yielding behaviour and to determine the displacement of the composite element, $u_{0,y}$, the relevant boundary conditions for stresses and displacements were used as well as the Treca yield condition. For the determination of the displacement, u^{my} , within the yielding effective matrix the change of the volume during deformation was considered providing a general relation between displacements and stresses, please see Ref. [9] for the details. The displacement condition at $r=r_p$ provided a transcendental equation for the yield limit, r_y , which is given for relatively stiff particles ($E_p \gg E_m$) by:

$$\ln\left(\frac{r_y}{r_p}\right) = \left[\frac{(1-\nu_m)}{2(1-2\nu_m)} + \frac{\tilde{\nu}}{3} \right] \left(\frac{r_y}{r_p} \right)^3 - s/2 - 1/3 \quad (10)$$

Solving this equation for r_y provides a numerical solution which can be expressed as a series expansion:

$$\frac{r_y}{r_p}(v_m, \nu, s) = \sum_n a_n s^n \quad (11)$$

The displacement at the outside of the composite element containing both yielding and elastic contributions was obtained as:

$$u_{0,y} = u^{me}(r=r_0) = \frac{r_0}{E_m} \sigma_0 \tilde{C}_{0,y}(s, \tilde{\nu}, \nu_m) = \frac{r_0}{E_m} \sigma_0 \left[\frac{\tilde{\nu}}{s} \left(\frac{r_y(s)}{r_p} \right)^3 (\nu_m - 1) + 1 - 2\nu_m \right] \quad (12)$$

5 ENERGY OF PLASTIC VOIDING

With the knowledge of the displacement at the composite element, $u_{0,y}$, the calculation of strain energy at yield, W_{my} , and energy density, η_{my} , become possible. The yielding energy is given by the product of applied force with corresponding displacement: $W_{my} = F_0 \Delta u = 4\pi r_0^2 \sigma_0 \Delta u$. Elastic deformations and yielding are superimposed within the matrix. If the composite element were to be unloaded, the remaining displacement, Δu , is appropriate for the calculation of yielding energy since it designs the displacement caused only by the yielding of the matrix. This is given approximately by the difference of the total displacements, $u_{0,y}$, at $r=r_0$ with matrix yielding and without yielding, u_0 , at the current stress state: $\Delta u = u_{0,y} - u_0$. Using these displacements provides for $E_p \gg E_m$:

$$\Delta u = \frac{r_0}{E_m} \sigma_0 \Delta \tilde{C}(s, \nu, \nu_m) = \frac{r_0}{E_m} \sigma_0 \left[\frac{1}{s} \tilde{\nu} (\nu_m - 1) \left(\frac{r_y}{r_p} \right)^3 + (1 - 2\nu_m) \left(1 - \frac{1 - \tilde{\nu}}{1 + 2\tilde{\nu}(1 - 2\nu_m)/(1 + \nu_m)} \right) \right] \quad (13)$$

With this value, as the lower limit for plastic displacement, the yielding energy around one particle was calculated as:

$$W_{my} = 4\pi r_0^2 \sigma_0 \Delta u = 4\pi r_0^3 \sigma_0^2 \Delta \tilde{C} / E_m \quad (14)$$

Multiplying this energy with the particle density, n_p , leads to the volume density of yielding energy:

$$\eta_{my} = n_p W_{my} = \frac{3\nu}{4\pi r_p^3} W_{my} = \frac{3\nu}{E_m \tilde{\nu}} \sigma_0^2 \Delta \tilde{C} \quad (15)$$

With this knowledge, the crack resistance caused by matrix yielding follows from Eq. (5) with the normalization $s = \sigma_0 / \sigma_{my}$:

$$R_{dz} = R_{my} = \frac{12\beta R_c E_c}{E_m} \frac{\nu}{\tilde{\nu}} \int_{s_{\min}}^{s_{\max}} \Delta \tilde{C}(s) (s)^{-1} ds \quad (16)$$

For the determination of the lower and upper bounds of integration the relation (5) was used. The lower limit, s_{\min} , was obtained as the smallest stress for initiation of yielding at $r=r_y=r_p$ and is given by:

$$s_{\min} = \frac{\sigma_{0,\min}}{\sigma_{my}} = \frac{2}{3} \left[\frac{1 + \nu_m}{2(1 - 2\nu_m)} + \tilde{\nu} \right] \quad (17)$$

For the upper bound that stress was used at which the whole matrix region between $r_p \leq r \leq r_0$ yields, i. e. inserting $r_y=r_0$ in Eq. (5) and solving for s_{\max} :

$$s_{\max} = \frac{\sigma_{0,\max}}{\sigma_{my}} = \frac{2}{3} \left(\frac{3a}{\tilde{\nu}} + \ln \tilde{\nu} - 1 \right) \quad \text{with} \quad a = \frac{(1 - \nu_m)}{2(1 - 2\nu_m)} + \frac{\tilde{\nu}}{3} \quad (18)$$

In the end, the composite crack resistance was derived by inserting Eq. (16) into Eq. (2) as:

$$\frac{R_c}{R_m} = \frac{\nu_m}{1 - \frac{12\beta E_c}{E_m} \frac{\nu}{\tilde{\nu}} \int_{s_{\min}}^{s_{\max}} \Delta \tilde{C}(s) (s)^{-1} ds} \quad (19)$$

According to the functionality of the above integral the composite crack resistance depends only on the elastic properties of components and the particle volume fraction. There is no dependence on particle size for the considered dissipation mechanism.

6 IMPLEMENTATION OF THE MODEL

The proposed model was applied for a hybrid composite consisting of rubber filled epoxy and additionally filled with glass spheres which have the following material properties: elastic modulus $E_p = 64 \text{ GPa}$ and Poisson's ratio $\nu_p = 0.2$. The elastic properties of the epoxy matrix are given by: $E_{m,0} = 3 \text{ GPa}$, $\nu_{m,0} = 0.35$ and a yield stress of $\sigma_{my} = 100 \text{ MPa}$ was used for the effective matrix consisting of neat matrix and rubber fillers. For a volume fraction of rubber particles of $\nu_r = 0.1$ within epoxy matrix this provides with the Halpin-Tsai equation for this effective matrix with $E_r/E_{m,0} \approx 0$: $E_m = E_{m,0}(1 + 2\eta\nu_r)/(1 - \eta\nu_r) = 2.57 \text{ GPa}$ with $\eta = (E_r/E_{m,0} - 1)/(E_r/E_{m,0} + 2) = -1/2$.

For the composite consisting of the effective matrix and glass particles, this relation was used again for the calculation of the composite modulus (cf. chapter 2). The matrix volume fraction in the crack plane was calculated for a lattice particle arrangement: $\nu_m = 1 - 1.21\nu^{2/3}$. The first aim was the calculation of the stress field and the radial displacement of the composite element. This generated the basis for calculating the yielding energy around one particle. As long as the yield condition is not yet satisfied the effective matrix behaves elastically. The radial and hoop stresses are shown in Fig. 5 as functions of the radial coordinate r/r_p for $s = s_{\min}$ (given in Eq. (17)), i.e. for the loading case where yielding starts at the particle radius: $r_y = r_p$. The yield law, Eq. (1), is just satisfied at this position and higher stresses, σ_0 , would cause matrix yielding there.

Figure 5. Distribution of radial and hoop stresses within the effective matrix of the composite element for the hydrostatic stress: $s = s_{\min}$. Yielding condition Eq. (1) is satisfied at $r/r_p = 1$, $\tilde{\nu} = 0.05$. Adapted from Ref. [9].

The result of crack resistance for the above given material properties is shown in Fig. 6 for the upper bound (s_{\max}) as given in Eq. (18) where only the given points were calculated. The solution of two different values of the parameter β which determines the size and shape of the yielding zone, ρ_y , are compared. Composite crack resistance increases at first with increasing microparticle content, ν ,

and then reaches a plateau and for higher values starts to decrease again. Such behaviour was measured for epoxy ternary composites filled with glass beads and rubber particles by Kinloch et al. [10].

Figure 6: Normalized composite crack resistance (fracture toughness) as a function of microparticle volume fraction, displaying the influence of matrix yielding within yielding zone; influence of the shape factor, β . Adapted from Ref. [9].

7 CONCLUSIONS

We conclude with a discussion of the model's main assumptions, how they might be relaxed, and what additional benefits might be gained.

The solution of the mechanical problem of a spherical particle within a spherical matrix provided the matrix yielding energy around one particle, where the Tresca yielding criterion was used. Subsequent summation of yielding energy density over all particles was carried out by replacing integration over the yielding zone size by integration over the hydrostatic stress. This enabled the derivation of an analytical equation of composite fracture toughness; otherwise a transcendental equation would have been obtained.

The main simplification used in the theoretical model was that the stress state in front of the crack of the composite material was assumed to be a hydrostatic one. It is known from linear elastic fracture mechanics that the stress state is multiaxial and depends on the distance from the crack tip and also the angle. Taking the more realistic stress field can formally be done, but the calculation of the matrix yielding energy around the microparticles becomes more elaborate. However, this would provide an additional advantage. One has to bear in mind that the modelling was carried out on a quasi-elastic basis; yielding was considered with the corresponding displacements derived with the elastic solution. The yielding processes around the microparticles are only allowed for the considered hydrostatic stress around the composite element by voiding of the rubber particles. The yield condition can be satisfied but the flow law was not considered. If the real triaxial stress field of the crack would be considered, then this limitation can be dropped because yielding can happen without the rubber particle voiding by corresponding deformations of the unsymmetrical triaxial stresses. The same effect would be reached if the plane stress situation in front of the crack would be applied, then a two-dimensional model can be used (very similar to the derivations above) and the perpendicular (z -direction) deformation may satisfy the constancy of volume during plastic deformation. Of course, a rigorous elastic-plastic calculation would improve the derivation, and other yielding laws instead of the Treca yield condition, and strain hardening should be taken into account.

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